

Cultural workers and cleaners: Striking back to back

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Autumn 2023 saw lecturers and cleaners at University of the Arts London (UAL) strike back-to-back for a combined 10 days. Represented by University College Union (UCU), UAL's teaching staff were out on industrial action from 25-29 September. The following week GMB union cleaners walked out, 2-6 October. Over the same period, there were UNISON cleaner and support staff strikes 21 universities across England and Scotland including Glasgow School of Art and Arts University Bournemouth.

Over the last decade in the UK, the culture sector has become increasingly radicalised and workers have been organising across occupational divides to together win better pay and conditions. United by a shared experience of exploitation, low pay and precarious employment, more and more, we've seen artists and curators, writers and journalists and university and college lecturers standing in solidarity with so-called "ancillary workers", like gallery front of house staff, exhibition technicians and museum security guards but cleaners have led the fight.

A Circuit of Ghosts: Hidden labour

In the 2013 article *Crisis in the Cleaning Sector*, Richard Braude likened the cleaning industry to a circuit of ghosts, a world of sleeplessness, forged documents, false names and invisible people. "For four years I only existed, I didn't live", a militant cleaner working at Senate House, told

Braude after he moved to London.

The role of culture is heavily contested, sometimes seen as virtue in its own right, art for arts sake, a preserve of the middle-classes, without social value or political function, but art has the power to expose injustice and artists have been using their art to shine a light on the hidden labour of cleaners working in the culture sector.

Formed of a group of independent artists and filmmakers, the Berwick Street Film Collective shot a 1975 documentary titled *Nightcleaners* to support a group of women office cleaners in their fight to unionise. The film features interviews with cleaners, scenes of cleaners at work and shots of May Hobbs, co-founder of the Cleaners' Action Group trade union, addressing crowds of women. This film is a familiar touchstone from the past but today's artists and filmmakers have made a lot of recent work in response to a new wave cleaner organising.

Back In-House,
directed by Sean
McSweyn (2022)

Sean McSweyn's 2022 film *Back In-House* documents UAL cleaners' fight against the exploitative and discriminatory practice of outsourcing. Fighting to be brought back in-house, as they were before, cleaners have been forced to change contractors multiple times

over recent years while working conditions have declined. "We just come here, do our job, what they expect us to do and that's it. Sometimes I feel they don't know that we exist", says a cleaner interviewed in the film, attesting to the way their labour is undervalued and underrecognised by their employer, the university directors and in part the teaching staff and students too. Through special editing techniques, cleaners appear as doubles of themselves, moving through spaces like ghosts in the night. The effect was achieved by cropping two shots on top of each other with no motion overlap. McSweyn told me, "The setting of these shots was crucial, placing the individual participants in the midst of the university's graduate art exhibitions, foregrounding their presence, their gaze, in an environment which otherwise demands their discretion."

Poet and community artist Phoebe Wagner has co-created a series of works with cleaning staff from around London. Speaking to me on the cleaners picket line at UAL, the artist told me, "For me and my work the most important thing is getting people to realise that the things they say are poetry." Her project *Cleaning in Progress* comprises a collection of audio-tours of the spaces cleaners polish, Hoover, tidy and dust, a testimony to hidden reparative work. Whereas McSweyn's film is about recognising invisibilised labour, Wagner's work is about finding beauty and power in everyday utterances. We hear from Sandra Farhani Cuesta, a cleaner at the Barbican Centre. She speaks in her own voice, in Spanish, her first language. The transcription provided reads: "For me my work means a lot as a foreigner and not being able to speak the language being able to work and have a stable income to live honestly that mentally gives you a lot of peace of mind". Sandra especially likes to interact with visitors. She speaks with homeless people, for example, the

rich, completely different types of people, a whole cross-section of society. She says, “this is not paid because [it] is not part of my tasks” but for Sandra it is “one of the most important things that I do in my job”.

Phoebe Wagner,
Cleaning in Progress
(2023) from the
group exhibition
Repair Redux in
Stratford, London
(2023).
Credit Carlo
Zambon.

Community Darkroom: Cleaner cultural production

For the cleaners too, cultural programming plays a vital role in promoting solidarity and growing the movement. On 12 July 2014, the Latin American Workers’ Association (LAWAS) and the Independent Workers Union of Great Britain (IWGB) presented photographs of the cleaners they represented and the conditions they worked in as part of exhibition about invisible labour at London’s Showroom gallery titled *Community Darkroom*.

IWGB represents low paid, precarious migrant workers. Re-founded in 2002 by Ernesto Leal, a communist from Chile who was tortured and sentenced to exile in 1976, now no longer in existence, LAWAS was a UK-based, migrant-led, self-organising group of Latin-American workers, mainly cleaners.

THE SHOW ROOM

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You are invited to the preview of

Werker 10

- Community Darkroom
- and
- An event with IWGB -

The Showroom is delighted to be working with Independent Workers of Great Britain for a one day event as part of Community Darkroom

Saturday 12 July 2014 12-5pm, presentations from 2pm

The IWGB (Independent Workers of Great Britain) are an independent union fighting for the rights of workers, predominantly cleaners, in London.

Over the last six years they have been involved in struggles against many of London's largest corporations. IWGB have been campaigning for a living wage, sick pay, pensions, and above all, for respect.

Please come to look, read and discuss with us. Only by learning from our histories can we fight for our futures

SOAS U
SOAS

FREE MUSIC and
Cleaners present...

Pulsating 9-piece Salsa group playing classic latin funk and soul as well as the old hi-toppers.

Friday 5th March 7-11pm

Entrance Free - but please make a donation to support the cleaners at UBS, who are organising to defend their rights against victimisation and exploitation. Cleaners' union activist Alberto Durango will be there to tell people about the campaign the cleaners are waging. Please give generously to support these badly exploited workers in their fight for justice!

myspace.com/

nuevo.rhythm.orchestra

LAWAS hosted meals with food from all around Latin America, also a lot of music and dance events, for example, a salsa night in support of a cleaners' strike at UBS bank, featuring the 9-piece group Nuevo Rhythm Orchestra. The logo of the Cleaners and Allied Independent Workers Union (CAIWU), which superseded LAWAS, shows three fists, one white, one brown, one black, the fighting hands of the world's workers. Around the fists there is a border, a Mesoamerican stepped-fret pattern called *xicalcolihqui*, representing the ancestral struggle that CAIWU continues today, Alberto Durango tells me, the union's general secretary.

Solidarity: "Sound arts technical staff support the cleaners' strike!"

Over the end of September, start of October, UAL cleaners and lecturers came together to support each other's strikes. On 29 September, mid-way through the UCU strikes, GMB cleaners held a joint event with the lecturers, bringing the two groups of activists together for a discussion and a screening of #PrecarityStory (2020), a documentary by Lorena Cervera and Isabel Seguí following a working day in the life of Isabel, who, at that time, was a cleaner, researcher, and teacher at the same British university. The following week, outside UAL's London College of Communication campus, teaching staff and students stood on the picket line with the cleaners, together waving GMB flags, drumming, blowing whistles, for a week, every morning 6-8 am. "UAL shame on you!" protesters chanted in unison. Messages of solidarity were left in the entrance way: "I'm a first year and I support your strike! You deserve fair conditions." "Sound arts technical staff support the cleaners' strike!" On Instagram, the Left Chinese Student Association made a post in support of

the campaign and 380 artists, writers, curators, lecturers and other cultural workers signed an open letter calling on UAL to end outsourcing and bring cleaners in-house. Signatories include Turner Prize-winner Tai Shani, White Pube art critic Zarina Muhammad and Gareth Spencer PCS Culture group president, leading voices in the struggle for a more equitable art and culture industry.

Taking the fight to culture: noise and confrontation

British artists have always been active in the labour movement, but over the last decade cleaners have brought radical union organising to museums, galleries and arts universities, leading the struggle for the rights of UK workers, not just in the culture sector but beyond.

On Saturday 14 April 2018, IWGB cleaners demonstrated at Tate Modern over potential redundancies facing their members at the London-based investment firm Ernst & Young (EY), a major sponsor of the gallery's Picasso *1932: Love, Fame, Tragedy* exhibition. Protesters, three dozen in number, filled the space with a carnival atmosphere, beating drums, blowing vuvuzelas. IWGB took the fight from the corporate quiet of EY's offices to the gallery, packed with weekend crowds. Tate were complicit with EY's mistreatment of its cleaners but they had no direct dispute with gallery. Radical cleaners unions use markedly different tactics to traditional unions. As UWW general secretary Petros Elia says, cleaner workplaces are small and organising in the sector requires bringing workers together in networks, rather than splitting up by branch, applying for recognition agreements and negotiating with management. He insists, effective action requires confrontation and disruption, beyond the picket line, more and more seen in museum and galleries.

IWGB Vamos Juntos Compañeros (2013). Independent Workers' Union of Great Britain and Latin American Workers' Association action at Barbican Centre in London 2013. Credit: Cleaners and Allied Independent Workers Union

In 2013, Barbican cleaners began a campaign for fair pay and respect. Subcontracted to outsourcing giant Mitie, employees reported incidences of racial abuse and intimidation. At the time, Barbican cleaners were on a poverty wage of £6.13 per hour and only entitled to the minimum legal rate of sick pay, which back then meant you received nothing for the first 3 consecutive days you missed work and just £96.35 per week after that, not enough to cover food and rent, forcing people to work sick or injured.

Independent Workers' Union of Great Britain and Latin American Workers' Association action at Barbican Centre in London (2013). Credit: Alberto Durango

Represented by LAWAS and IWGB, later United Voices of the World (UVW) union, the cleaners went on strike, staged protest after protest, occupied the Barbican's foyer, filled the building with noise, flags, banners, collective strength and determination. After an embattled three-year struggle, in 2016 Barbican cleaners won the London Living Wage for all facilities staff in the City of London Corporation, the Barbican's parent company, and the workers became some of the first workers in the country to demand and fight for full pay sick pay.

Class separation: Impossible distances

While IWGB and UVW's radical tactics have been effective, they might not necessarily work throughout the culture sector where pay and conditions are massively unequal across class, race, gender, education background.

At the moment, for example, UAL cleaners have received a lot of support from casualised lecturers, who share similar experiences of casualisation – nearly a third of all UAL academics are hourly paid – but a UCU-UAL rep told me tenured professor on secure, permanent contracts and higher rates of pay have been far less present on the picket line.

Culture workers are pitted against each other, subjected to familiar 'divide and rule' tactics and the stakes of taking action are far higher for unpapered migrants. What are the limits of solidarity?

For Berwick Street Film Collective member Marc Karlin, *Nightcleaners* was about distance: the distance between the migrant cleaners working through the night and, in his estimation, the "middle class" reps from the Women's Liberation Movement recruiting for the trade unions; it was also about distance between the cleaners and the artists

behind the lens, the realities of doing the job day in, day out, and the carefully choreographed shots featured in the film. As Karlin commented “I think with *Nightcleaners* what we did was we revealed the situation of the nightcleaners on the one hand and on the other, the impossibility of capturing those lives”.

Industrial unionism: One shop, one union

Flyer for Nuevo Rhythm Orchestra event in support of Justice4Cleaners campaign. Latin American Workers' Association archive collection at MayDay Rooms. Credit: Latin American Workers' Association

There may be distances between us but the cleaners and lectures at at UAL show us that we can bring cultural workers together, without eliding our differences.

Whereas craft unions separate workers by occupation, the culture sector should follow the principle of industrial unionism, underpinned by the saying, “One shop, one union”. Industrial unions unite every worker who shares the same employer or the same in the workplace, bringing a sector together to form one big, collective movement.

Cleaners belong to same the industry as the rest of culture workers, they make up part of the same supply chain. If the bins fill up and the rubbish piles high, the lecturers can't teach, the museums can't open. Remove any one link from the chain and the whole system begins to break down.

“Ancillary workers” are essential to every cultural workers fight for dignity in work. Only when the culture sector comes together, as whole, can we confront the power of our employers and achieve a better way of life.

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